

References

1. S. P. SINGH, S. S. PARMAR and V. I. STENBERG, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1978, 15, 9; S. P. SINGH, S. KUMAR, B. R. PANDEY and S. S. PARMAR, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1978, 15, 175.
2. The Merck Index, edited by P. G. STUECHER, Merck & Co., 1968.
3. J. B. STOTHER, "Carbon-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic Press, 1972.
4. G. C. LEVY and G. L. NELSON, "Carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy for Organic Chemists", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972.

Kinetics and Mechanism of Chlorination of Some Activated Aromatic Systems by Chloramine-T

P. S. RADHAKRISHNA MURTI and H. P. PANDA

Department of Chemistry, Berhampur University,
Berhampur-760 007, Orissa, India

Manuscript received 14 February 1979, accepted 18 October 1979

KINETICS of chlorination of anisoles¹, aromatic amines² and phenylacetates³ have been reported earlier. The present communication deals with the chlorination of 1-naphthol, 2-naphthol, 1-methoxynaphthalene, 2-methoxynaphthalene, 1-acetoxynaphthalene and 2-acetoxynaphthalene in aqueous acetic acid medium by chloramine-T.

Materials and Methods :

Chloramine-T was of (M & B) analar grade. 1- and 2-naphthols were B.D.H. samples and purified before use. 1-methoxynaphthalene, 2-methoxynaphthalene, 1-acetoxynaphthalene and 2-acetoxynaphthalene were prepared according to the method of Vogel⁴. Standard iodometric procedure was adopted for estimating chloramine-T volumetrically using starch as indicator. All the experiments were carried out in duplicate. The results were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$ error.

Results and Discussion

The reactions are first order in CAT. The pseudo first order rate constant increases on increasing the substrate concentration. In case of naphthols and methoxynaphthalenes, the order with respect to substrate has been found to be fractional in the concentration range 0.001M to 0.005M above which the order in the substrate changes to unity (Table 1). The double reciprocal plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[S]$ for each substrate falls in to two distinct lines, one passing through origin and the other having a finite intercept on the rate axis thus showing a complex dependence of rate on the substrate in the lower concentration range. This complex behaviour is however absent at higher concentration of the substrate ($>0.005M$) and a total second order kinetics is evident from

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING THE [SUBSTRATE] ON THE REACTION RATE

		Temp. 35°C.		
		[CAT]=0.0005M, [HClO ₄]=0.0125M,		
Substrate	% of HOAc	10 ³ × k ₁ [Substrate] M	10 ⁵ × k ₁ sec ⁻¹ w.r.t. CAT	10 ³ × k ₂ ' 1. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
1-naphthol	20	1.20	10.90	—
		2.01	15.49	—
		2.80	20.30	—
		4.16	23.90	—
		4.93	26.52	5.33
		7.26	37.44	5.15
2-naphthol	20	10.18	51.52	5.06
		14.85	73.47	4.95
		5.15	43.97	8.53
		10.05	85.55	8.51
1-methoxy-naphthalene	50	14.78	113.30	7.67
		5.15	3.31	0.65
		10.71	7.10	0.66
2-methoxy-naphthalene	50	15.37	10.84	0.70
		4.90	1.70	0.34
		7.53	2.23	0.30
1-acetoxy-naphthalene	50	10.09	3.23	0.32
		5.00	2.05	—
		7.50	2.33	—
2-acetoxy-naphthalene	50	10.00	2.67	—
		15.00	3.45	—
		5.00	1.67	—
		10.00	2.37	—
		20.00	3.66	—

fair constancy in the second order rate constant (k_2 , 1. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹) over a wide variation of concentration of the substrate. 1- and 2-acetoxynaphthalenes exhibit a fractional dependence (0.55) in the entire range studied.

The effect of acidity has been found to be marginal for naphthols and methoxynaphthalenes. But in 1- and 2-acetoxynaphthalenes the reaction rate is insensitive to added H⁺ ions up to 0.05M of HClO₄ above which there is pronounced acceleration (Table 2). It appears that at higher acidity the carbonyl oxygen of the acetoxy group probably gets protonated and both the protonated and unprotonated molecules participate in the reaction.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACIDITY

		Temp. 35°C.	
		[CAT]=0.0005M, HOAc : 50% V/V	
		[Substrate]=0.01M	
Substrate	[HClO ₄]M	10 ³ × k ₁ ' sec ⁻¹	
1-acetoxynaphthalene	0.0125	2.67	
	0.025	2.56	
	0.05	2.59	
	0.10	4.01	
	0.20	6.90	
2-acetoxynaphthalene	0.0125	2.37	
	0.025	2.67	
	0.05	2.77	
	0.10	4.22	
	0.20	6.73	

An increase in the dielectric constant increases the rate and addition of neutral salts has no effect on the rate pointing to a dipole dipole type of reaction.

pH profile :

The effect of pH on the reaction rate and the nature of the CAT species have been investigated, first in acetic acid sodium acetate buffer medium and then in pure aqueous medium.

Addition of sodium acetate enhances the rate (Table 3). In presence of 0.02M NaOAc and 20%

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF pH IN SODIUM ACETATE ACETIC ACID BUFFER MEDIUM

Solvent=20% HOAc			Temp. 35°C.	
10 ³ [1-naphthol]M	[NaOAc]M	10 ⁴ [CAT]M	10 ⁴ × k ₁ sec ⁻¹ w.r.t. CAT	k ₂ " 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ w.r.t. CAT
7.35	0.02 (pH=2.5)	4.675	9.64	—
		6.50	10.02	—
		10.05	10.18	—
7.04	0.20 (pH=3.5)	4.72	—	3.50
		7.15	—	3.59
		9.52	—	3.60
		14.10	—	3.55

HOAc the order with respect to CAT is unity. Surprisingly in 0.2M NaOAc and 20% HOAc the reaction is second order with respect to CAT as evidenced by a good linearity in the plot of 1/[CAT] vs time and a fair constancy in the second order rate constant (k₂" lit. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹) with respect to CAT over a threefold increase in [CAT]. This peculiar behaviour of the CAT species might originate from the effective pH of the medium. In 0.02M NaOAc and 20% HOAc (pH=2.5) the hydrolysed species RNHCl operates, whereas in 0.2M NaOAc and 20% HOAc (pH=3.5) the equilibrium,

(where R=CH₃C₆H₄SO₂-) causes the facile disproportionation of CAT to dichloramine-T (DCT). The existence of DCT as the reacting species at pH=3.5 is well supported by the work of Mahadevappa *et al.*⁵ in the study of physicochemical properties of CAT and of Higuchi *et al.*⁶ in the active halogen transfer between N-chlorosuccinimide and *p*-toluene sulphonamide at pH 3.55.

We have further observed that in pure aqueous medium (Table 4),

(a) the order with respect to CAT is perfectly unity up to pH 2.5 ;

(b) at pH 3.5 the order with respect to CAT is two ;

TABLE 4—pH PROFILE IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM			
[1-naphthol]=0.001M			
pH value	10 ⁴ [CAT]M	10 ⁴ × k ₁ sec ⁻¹ w.r.t. CAT	Temp. 35°C. k ₂ " 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ w.r.t. CAT
1.9	2.55	4.56	—
	4.93	5.09	—
	7.36	5.39	—
2.5	2.95	16.40	—
	5.23	17.64	—
	7.50	19.80	—
3.5	2.05	—	22.20
	4.05	—	23.87
	6.27	—	22.10
4.5	2.55	120.80	—
	4.96	126.74	—
	7.21	133.90	—
5.4	2.32	37.06	—
	4.63	41.61	—
	6.96	43.52	—
6.85	2.42	22.68	—
	4.71	23.33	—
	6.95	23.01	—
8.6	5.00	16.24	—
10.0	5.00	3.79	—

(c) at pH 4.5 the order with respect to CAT again becomes unity ; the rate profile attains a maximum value at this pH and there after the rate decreases as one goes to higher pH ;

(d) there is a complete breakdown of reactivity at pH 10.

Thus it appears that the hydrolysed species RNHCl is important till pH 2.5. The strikingly second order dependence at pH 3.5 clearly shows that DCT is the active halogenating species at this pH range. The enormous increase in the rate and the first order dependence on CAT at pH 4.5 suggest a monomeric species. Mushran *et al.*⁷ have postulated HOCl as the species at pH 4.5. The order of reactivity of the species observed is, HOCl > DCT > RNHCl.

Mechanism and rate law :

In accordance with the observed experimental data it is possible to postulate the following mechanism for substrate concentration below 0.005M in case of naphthols and methoxynaphthalenes, taking the hydrolysed species RNHCl (pH ≤ 2.5) as the halogenating agent.

(where R' = H or CH₃)

Applying a steady state treatment to the complex one arrives at the rate law :

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}'] [\text{CAT}]_T}{(k_{-2} + k_3) + k_2 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}]}$$

This explains the fractional order with respect to substrate in the lower concentration range. At higher concentrations of the substrate the double reciprocal plots pass through origin. The reaction therefore proceeds either through a direct halogen transfer from RNHCl or through a loose complex whose stability constant is very low. Therefore the rate law assumes the form :

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = k_2' [\text{CAT}]_T [\text{substrate}]$$

The observed direct fractional dependence on acidity in case of acetoxynaphthalenes can be rationalised by invoking the protonation of the carbonyl oxygen of the acetoxy group in an equilibrium step prior to formation of the transition complex in the pre-rate determining step. Thus :

Taking the protonation equilibrium in to consideration and applying a steady state treatment to the transition complex one arrives at the rate law :

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = \frac{k_3 k_2 K [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T [\text{CAT}]_T [\text{H}^+]}{(k_{-2} + k_3) + \{k_{-2} + k_3 + k_2 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T\} K [\text{H}^+]}$$

(where $R' = \text{CO.CH}_3$)

This explains the fractional dependence on the substrate and a direct fractional dependence on acidity. At lower acidity the protonation equilibria is probably not much pronounced. Hence only the unprotonated acetoxy compound reacts. The rate law would therefore become,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T [\text{CAT}]_T}{(k_{-2} + k_3) + k_2 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T}$$

The product analysis has been done in case of 1-naphthol and 2-naphthol. 1-Naphthol gives 4-chloro-1-naphthol as the major product alongwith trace amounts of 2-chloroisomer. 2-Naphthol exclusively gives 1-chloro-2-naphthol.

References

1. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and B. M. SASMAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16(A), 598.
2. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and M. D. PRASAD RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14(A), 485.

3. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and B. M. SASMAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 17(A), 181.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. Edition, E.L.B.S., 1971, p. 669, 670.
5. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and R. SWAMI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 7, 468.
6. T. HIGUCHI, K. IKEDA and A. HUSSAIN, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1968, 1031.
7. S. P. MUSHRAN, R. M. MEHROTRA and R. SANDEHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 594.

Studies on the Complexes of Uranium(IV), Thorium(IV) and Lanthanum(III) Acetates with *p*-Aminobenzoic acid, *m*-Aminobenzoic acid, Benzilic acid and Phthalic acid

MANGAL SINGH and AJAIB SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab, India

Manuscript received 4 October 1978, revised 24 September 1979, accepted 19 November 1979

U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes with some chelating ligands have been synthesised recently¹⁻⁵. Under the present investigation complexes of U(IV), Th(IV) and La(III) with title ligands have been isolated and characterized on the basis of IR, electronic and magnetic susceptibility data.

Experimental

U(OAc)₄ and Th(OAc)₄ were prepared as reported in literature^{6,7}. La(OAc)₃ (BDH), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (Riedel), *m*-aminobenzoic acid (BDH), benzilic acid (E. Merck) and phthalic acid (BDH) were used as such. Absolute ethanol and dry petroleum ether (40-60°) were used.

Preparation of Complexes :

U(OAc)₄ or Th(OAc)₄ and the ligand (*p*-aminobenzoic acid or *m*-aminobenzoic acid or benzilic acid) in 1 : 4 ratio, La(OAc)₃ and the ligand in 1 : 3 ratio and U(OAc)₄ or Th(OAc)₄ and phthalic acid in 1 : 2 ratio were refluxed in ethanol, when the complex precipitated. The complexes were washed with ethanol and petroleum ether and dried in vacuum. However, benzilic acid complexes remained in solution and the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure when very fine shining crystals were left behind as residue.

The refluxing time, colour and analytical results of the complexes are given in Table 1. IR spectra of the complexes and the ligands were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 Infrared Spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra of U(IV) complexes were recorded on a SP 700 Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities of U(IV) chelates were measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance.